

The Four Corners on River Road

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Executive Summary

In 2015 Lane Transit District (LTD), in partnership with the City of Eugene, regional agencies, and the Eugene-Springfield community launched the MovingAhead project. The objective of the project was to identify important streets in the Eugene-Springfield area and determine what transportation investments were needed.¹ The MovingAhead team identified five key corridors and considered the costs and benefits of a variety of transportation investments for each. The MovingAhead Executive Summary was published in September of 2018 to inform the community of where this partnership planned to focus their investments over the next decade. River Road was named as one of the five corridors along with Coburg Road, Highway 99, 30th Avenue to LCC and MLK Jr. Blvd./Centennial Blvd. Consequently, a year later, the Sustainable City Year Program and LTD formed a partnership with University of Oregon's Public Planning, Policy, and Management department. The Community and Regional Planning students were asked to conceptualize, design, and propose a site plan for one of the bus stops along the River Road corridor. This report will put forth our proposal for the Old Station site (Census Tract 28) on the Northeast corner of River Road and River Avenue.

**Our vision is influenced by the question:
“Where do we want to go together?”**

The River Road community is at a critical turning point in its history and this is an important moment to decide what the future looks like for the River Road neighborhood. Our vision is to create a catalyst site on the Northeast corner of River Road and River Avenue that will honor the heritage and history of River Road and help solidify the neighborhood brand. Currently, the NE corner is operating as LTD's main bus station on the existing corridor and it shares the lot with a vacant building, once a furniture store. It is just south of the Beltline Highway and adjacent to a McDonald's drive-through.

**Our vision for this site is big – one that will take up to
20 years of implementation over four phases.**

We were encouraged to think and dream big and believe that through collaborative public-private partnerships, community engagement and ingenuity, redevelopment on the NE corner could spur redevelopment on all of the other corners. Inspired to take on this challenge and think of how this area could transform, we came up with our proposal for this site: “The Four Corners of River Road.” Together, these four corners will help create a walkable, vibrant, safe, and sustainable community. This will be achieved by providing access to transit, affordable housing, community gathering spaces, cultural programming, and economic opportunity.

Through extensive analysis and research, we gained valuable insight into what has helped form the River Road community, who has contributed to that formation and what it looks like today. We researched the neighborhood history, cultural background, current demographics and needs of its residents, and conducted a site analysis to further understand the locational context within which we were working. We reviewed and analyzed various plans including the River Road Santa Clara Neighborhood Plan, the Eugene 2035 Transportation Plan, the MovingAhead Plan, and the City of Eugene Comprehensive Plan. Through this, we identified common themes which influenced our recommendations aligning with the community's visions and broader planning goals for the area.

We noticed an emphasis on place-based planning wherein community values significantly inform planning objectives. The provision of a diverse, affordable array of housing types. A focus on context-responsive infill throughout the transit corridor and in residential areas with compact housing options to address the “missing middle.” Additional commonalities included increasing economic prosperity, fostering regional identity, promoting the overall health of community members, and improving transit safety.

Our goal with this project was to focus on how we could account for future growth while maintaining the neighborhood's integrity and culture. This informed our four main planning objectives: improve pedestrian and cyclist safety, engage the community in placemaking efforts, promote sustainability and prioritize affordability

The overall design concept focuses on four areas: affordability, connectivity, placemaking and sustainability. This report details each of these concepts and includes background information as to why these four concepts are relevant for the River Road community at this time as well as offers relevant case studies and ideas for implementation. Our recommendation includes multi-family housing and a more vibrant street corner. This section of the corridor is particularly outdated in building design and infrastructure, so implementing a plan that adds vibrancy and culture to the area is key.

In order to fortify our concepts, we suggest a flexible and comprehensive approach to implementation:

- LTD decides to sell or lease the land
- Moving the bus stop to the Southeast Corner of River Road and River Avenue
- Creating opportunities for community engagement related to placemaking efforts
- Propose mixed-use buildings that fit within current zoning
- Incorporate sustainable efforts into updated urban design

The River Road area has the potential to transform from a place that you drive through at high-speeds on your way to somewhere else to a destination. A place where both visitors and neighborhood members notice the strides that were made to include community stakeholders in decision making. An intersection that prioritizes pedestrian safety and ensures that high schoolers have an easy path to get to school. A

residential neighborhood that provides diverse housing options, a commercial environment that values local businesses and placemaking features that honor the heritage, history and future of the area. With commitment from The City and Lane Transit District, "The Four Corners on River Road" can provide more community gathering spaces, affordable housing, diverse economic opportunities and sustainable values; efforts which will benefit residents, businesses, developers and community organizations for years to come.

Our Site: Old Station – near the on-ramp to the Randy Pape Beltline.

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

Site History and Background

The area of the modern-day River Road neighborhood lies on indigenous land of the Kalapuya Native American tribe.² The fertile soil along the banks of the Willamette River made it an important agricultural area for the tribes for generations. In the 1840's and 1850's Anglo settlers from the United States arrived to the area via the Oregon Trail. This led to the formal establishment of the City of Eugene in 1853.³ Early settlers to the area utilized the River Road area for farming, just as the Native Americans had before them. In fact, the modern thoroughfare of River Road is located along an old Kalapuya trail. Most farming in the area consisted of small locally owned grain farms and various orchards. The construction of the Oregon & California Railway in 1871 led to the establishment of the Roosevelt Railyard on the western edge of the River Road neighborhood and provided a way for the local farmers goods to get to markets beyond the Eugene-Springfield area.⁴ The area remained rural and agrarian until the 1950's post-war economic boom which caused the city of Eugene to expand with new subdivisions. In the decades since, the River Road Neighborhood has continued to grow, its remaining small farms dwindled in number every year until they eventually disappeared. The completion of the Randy Pape Beltline Highway in the area in 1970 brought even further growth and now serves as the boundary between the Santa Clara neighborhood to the North and the River Road neighborhood to the South.² When the 1982 Metro plan established that all areas within the Eugene-Springfield Urban Growth Boundary be annexed by the city, deep resistance from the residents emerged. This has led to an area with complicated jurisdictions as a majority of the neighborhood is now under city jurisdiction, but a number of sites still fall under Lane County jurisdiction in somewhat of a patchwork pattern.² The area in the present day is a suburban community of aging subdivisions and shopping centers ripe for change.⁴

Historic Photograph of River Road

Source: Eugene Historic Review Board (2005)

History of Planning and Policy in the Area

The history of planning and policy in the area goes back to the 1890's when the land was originally subdivided into large land claims of 640 or 320 acres.⁴ Most of these land claims were developed as family farms which subdivided as they were passed down from generation to generation or sold to new owners. Many of the roads in the neighborhood were built along these old property lines. The area was first platted for subdivisions in the 1910's with modest growth till the 1930's. The area boomed postwar and took on many of the characteristics it has today.⁴ More modern plans for the area include the 1982 Metro Plan, the 1987 Urban Facilities Plan, The current Eugene-Springfield Metro Plan, Envision Eugene, LTD's Moving Ahead and most recently the River Road & Santa Clara Neighborhood Plan.

Old Station Site Analysis

Site Location

For our project, the site location and its proximity to different hubs in the Eugene/Springfield area are important elements in drafting our proposal. Our site includes the Old LTD Park-and-Ride Station on the corner of River Road and River Avenue. Our initial focus was on the parcel of land available between the intersection of River Road and River Avenue, near the Randy Pape Beltline in Old Station. But as LTD has discussed possibly selling the Old Station land we look at the future development prospects of this land acting as a catalyst to the other four corners and the neighborhood surrounding this intersection. This intersection near the highway is one of the busiest with one of the highest accident rates in the area. A redevelopment plan is needed for the neighborhood to mitigate transportation related safety issues, revitalize the outdated infrastructure, and connect the neighborhood with its natural environment.

Macro View

It is located at the heart of the city of Eugene with a distance of 4.3 miles from Eugene Airport, 4 miles from the University of Oregon: and 5.6 miles from Springfield (Figure 1). With its proximity to these hubs and connectivity of the transit lines, Old Station is an attractive location for future residents to move to.

Old Station Site: River Road and Silver Lane Intersection

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

FIGURE 1. MACRO VIEW MAP OF OLD STATION – EUGENE, OREGON, 2019

Source: Google Earth and Aqsa Khan (2019)

SWOT Analysis

In analyzing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats (SWOT) of the area, we were able to determine where improvements need to be made and where the neighborhood already has optimal infrastructure and opportunity for revitalization. The purpose of this analysis is to identify areas of improvement in the neighborhood in terms of social aspects, build environment, and the natural environment. This was completed early on in our proposal development process and helped to inform our recommendations for the Old Station site. The below chart outlines key elements of the SWOT of Old Station with more detail on the critical focus points following the chart.

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

Strengths	Weaknesses	Opportunities	Threats
<p>Surrounded by neighborhood of single-family and apartment homes.</p> <p>K-12 schools in proximity to the bus stop</p> <p>Established bus stop with parking lot, large space to work with</p> <p>Buildable land on the four corners</p> <p>Public land providing amenities for residents</p>	<p>Outdated urban design, unattractive infrastructure</p> <p>High traffic area and congestion at peak hours</p> <p>Issue of safety at this intersection</p> <p>Lack of neighborhood vibrancy</p> <p>Water treatment plant nearby</p>	<p>Make school commutes safer and more accessible for students</p> <p>Make bike lanes and pedestrian crossing more prominent and safer</p> <p>Connection to the river bike path</p> <p>Develop affordable housing units on underutilized strip mall land, starting with the Old Station</p>	<p>Proximity to Beltline highway increases noise, safety, and traffic congestion</p> <p>Fast food chains in the surrounding area, contribute to congestion, neighborhood culture, etc.</p>

Bicycle and Pedestrian Access

Goal 4 of the River Road/Santa Clara Neighborhood Plan⁶ (hereafter referred to as the Neighborhood Plan) seeks to achieve a safe, efficient, and accessible multi-modal transportation system for the area. Considering this goal, we focus on enhancing the transportation network for one aspect of our site plan. Pedestrian and bicycle safety are a significant concern for our site due to its proximity to the freeway. The high traffic of this area results in congestion at peak travel hours and issues of safety at the intersection of River Road and River Avenue (the highest automobile accident rate in Lane County). Plenty of development opportunities exist for this topic, including enhancing pedestrian and bicycle access to the river, improving pedestrian safety near the Beltline area, and increasing walkability throughout the neighborhood. Ways to achieve these goals include adding or enhancing crosswalks near significant traffic areas and creating dedicated cycling lanes where needed.

We've specifically identified the following aspects as existing constraints and opportunities relating to this topic for our site. To enhance safe transportation near the Beltline, we support the Neighborhood Plan's identified action to build a bicycle/pedestrian bridge across the Beltline (near the North Eugene High School location).⁶ This could take the form of a tunnel beneath the freeway near Ruby Avenue and Sterling Drive. Additional steps are the addition of pedestrian signals at school crossings to ensure student safety. At the dangerous intersection of River Road and River Avenue we advocate for the installation of a raised crosswalk (to slow down drivers and increase awareness of pedestrians in the area). Pedestrian safety can be further enhanced by the installation of sidewalks near business, recreation, and school areas where needed. For bicycle safety, we propose creating dedicated bike lanes along

major collector roads and main routes to schools. To enhance access to the river, we see an opportunity to create a bike path that provides access to the Willamette River and connects the neighborhood to the greater Ruth Bascom Riverbank Path System. Regarding the existing physical structure at the Old Station, we see this as an opportunity to redevelop the station into a pedestrian-focused area, with a bicycle share and dockless scooter storage for enhanced mobility. We would like to incorporate a new bike path on the north facing side of the site. This area could be further enhanced with the installation of a park/playground area to enhance the overall neighborhood character and vibrancy.

Protected Bike Lanes in Portland, Oregon

Source: Bike Portland (2018)

Existing zoning of area

Old Station is primarily zoned as C-2 Community Commercial (Figure 4). This classification is intended to allow for community commercial uses in the district.⁷ The existing zoning provides all the opportunity and flexibility needed to create more mixed use in this neighborhood. Therefore, we are not proposing any land use or zoning changes. District areas zoned as C-2 range in size from 5 to 40 acres. Community commercial uses encompass a wide variety, including retail, entertainment, office, and service needs to meet the needs of a large residential population. Housing use is allowed in C-2 zones, with a high degree of flexibility. Residential housing can be built on individual lots, shared lots, and in clusters with shared parking.⁷

Additionally, a significant proportion of our site is also designated as Public Land. Current uses for these areas are schools, wastewater services, and riverfront parks. These lands further serve as an asset to our site, providing important amenities such as access to education, water treatment facilities, and recreational open spaces.

FIGURE 4. EUGENE ZONING

Source: Eugene, Lane County, Lane Council of Governments, and Springfield (2015)

Environmental Context

According to the Envision Eugene⁸ and River Road Corridor Study⁹ the site is expected to experience:

- Reduced snowpack
- Increased flooding
- Drier summers
- The potential of more people coming in due to global warming effects in the other regions

Challenges

In addition to population growth, the prices for natural resources are expected to rise dramatically. This not only affects the rise in fuel and electricity prices but as Oregon thrives on the timber industry and natural organic food resources so the change will increase the amount of economic prosperity in the region.¹⁰

Flooding in Alton Baker Park – Eugene, Oregon

Source: Annette Truck Anderson (2019)

Solutions

In terms of our design, we are preparing for the incoming potential migrations by proposing low cost, multi-family housing in the form of mixed-use buildings, and spaces for pocket parks and vertical gardens. While designing the buildings, we have to consider the threats and risks of flooding so strategizing according to the new design ideas and materials especially for the piling and foundations of the densities being built. The Riverfront area and the river bike pathways have to be kept at a certain elevation in case of flooding. Also, with the summers being drier, having water fountains near bike pathways and pedestrian crossings will be beneficial. Lastly, planting more trees and native vegetation in the neighborhood, especially along the built densities, pedestrian crossings, and roads will enhance neighborhood vibrancy while contributing to the environmental elements of the area.

Ruth Bascom Riverbank Trail

Source: Vern Rogers (201)

Socioeconomic Profile

Demographic trends

The demographic and overall socioeconomic profile of Old Station influences the proposed improvements to the area, as we hope to cater to the needs of the current and future residents of the neighborhood. Old Station has experienced population growth over the last ten years and is expected to continue this pattern. Over the next 5 years, Social Explorer has projected population in our census tract to increase by about 8% or 383 people.¹² The neighborhood experienced 9% growth from 2010 to 2017 according to ACS estimate data (Table 1).

This is a higher rate than its larger encompassing regions, Eugene, Lane County, and Oregon, which shows that it is attracting more people to the area for various reasons. This increase has a significant impact on housing, the local school system, and other community services. Many factors may contribute to this increase, including job opportunities, housing affordability, and educational opportunities. This area offers affordable housing, a K-12 school district with an International Baccalaureate high school program, and grocery outlets. It is an attractive area for families, and low-income residents because of the affordable housing options and family-centric services available.

TABLE 1. POPULATION CHANGE BY GEOGRAPHY

Geographic Area	2010	2017	Change	Percent change
Oregon	3,831,074	4,025,127	194,053	5.1%
Lane County	351,715	363,471	11,756	3.3%
Eugene	156,185	163,135	6,950	4.4%
River Road CT 28	4,189	4,566	377	9.0%

Sources:

Census 2010, Social Explorer Table T1

ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Social Explorer Table A00001

FIGURE 5. HISPANIC OR LATINO AND NON-WHITE PERCENT OF POPULATION DEMOGRAPHICS – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Sources:

Census 2010, Social Explorer Tables B03003 and T54

ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Social Explorer Tables B03003 and A03001

Hispanic/Latino and Non-White Population

Hispanic/Latino and non-white residents in Oregon show interesting results when compared with each other. Overall, the Hispanic/Latino population has increased since 2010, but the non-white population has decreased everywhere but Eugene (Figure 5). The non-white population in the Old Station neighborhood has decreased by roughly 4% since 2010. With the increase in population in this area, the decrease in non-white residents can be a result of the increase in white residents moving to the area.

Population is younger in our neighborhood.

Figure 6¹ shows that 60.1% of the population in Eugene is between 18 and 54 years of age. The city of Eugene has a higher percentage of 18- to 24-year-old residents than the other geographies which is likely due to the University of Oregon population. Our neighborhood has a very low percent of the population in this age range which shows that university-age students do not live here, and rather, adults above the age of 25 who are likely employed full-time and need to commute to work. Of note as well, is the higher percent of population under the age of 5 (8.5%) in our neighborhood compared with the larger geographic regions. Having young children in the area shows a need for services such as daycares and community centers and opportunity to further develop these family-oriented amenities and bring more traffic to the K-12 schools on Silver Lane.

FIGURE 7. FAMILY POVERTY RATES – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Source: ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Social Explorer Table A13002

Income/Poverty level

This data in Figure 7 explaining the percentage of families below the poverty level shows that our census tract has higher rates than the rest of the Oregon geographies we examined. It can be inferred from this information that these families may rely on public transportation more than those above the poverty level and therefore, a need for improved transportation, along with other social/public services is prevalent. Majority of households below the poverty line have a female head of house, with no husband present. According to Figure 7, about 5% have children under the age of 18. This shows the importance of safe public transit systems and safe public access in the neighborhood, for residents, and especially for children in this area. Making the Old Station, specifically the bus intersection safe for families and children to cross and to interact with on a regular basis will make the neighborhood more community focused.

¹ See Figure 6 in the Appendix

Educational attainment

In adults over the age of 25, 35% have completed some college and only 18.4% have graduated with a bachelor's degree. Educational attainment and income level generally relate to each other, so it is not surprising to see the majority of the population has graduated from high school or has only finished some college with the lower overall income levels in the neighborhood. Majority of the Old Station population is over the age of 25 with high school diplomas or some college completed, according to Figure 8.² This helps to explain why such a large percent of the population makes less than \$45,000 annually and why a portion of households live below the poverty line. It is more difficult to make a livable wage with a high school diploma alone. With this information, it can be inferred that there is a need for affordable housing and access to public transportation at our site.

Source: KVAL (2019)

Demographic Implications

Upon analyzing the community profile above, we found that it provides compelling data for the Old Station study area. The results highlight an area that has the potential for growth: a large percentage of the population is young and educated. However, there are some significant economic implications in this area that may impact growth and need to be taken into consideration as proposals for development are made. For our study area, it was crucial to examine the racial diversity of the community our site is in, as well as the economic characteristics of this community. We focused on the social and economic characteristics of this community profile as we began to propose ideas for development, long-term visions and site-analysis. Our team considered the questions of access and equity in development proposals and considered what proposals will function best for this demographic. In an attempt to understand the character of the community, it was important to factor in the age distribution of our study area in combination with race/ethnicity and potential economic barriers. Each of these demographics contributes to how the character of the River Road community is fostered, and we kept these numbers and percentages in mind as a reflection of the people who live in and occupy these neighborhoods around Old Station.

River Road Community Members

Source: River Road Santa Clara Neighborhood Plan (2019)

² See Figure 8 in the Appendix

TABLE 2. OVERALL EMPLOYMENT – UNITED STATES AND LANE COUNTY, 2001-2016

LANE COUNTY						
Sector	2001		2016		Change	
	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	#	%
Total employment (number of jobs)	185,118	100%	204,742	100%	19,624	10.6%

UNITED STATES						
Sector	2001		2016		Change	
	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	#	%
Total employment (number of jobs)	165,519,200	100%	193,668,400	100%	28,149,200	17.0%

Source: NAICS

Economic trends

As of 2018, Lane County has an estimated population of **375,120**, making it the fourth largest county in the state of Oregon.¹³ The major employers in the area include PeaceHealth Medical Group, University of Oregon, and the Eugene School District, among others.¹⁴ As part of this study, we analyzed employment trends in Lane County, Oregon and the United States. From this, we gathered the below trends.

Overall Employment Growth

As we moved forward in proposing alternative plans and development strategies for Lane Transit District’s River Road Corridor project, it was important that we look at the economic profile of the region in order to have a better understanding of the economic factors that impact our planning area. Table 2 shows the total employment numbers and percentages and the change in employment between 2001 and 2016 in Lane County and the United States. It also reveals that between 2001 and 2016 **28,149,200 jobs** were created in the United States, meaning the National Average Growth Rate for this timeframe was **17%**. Comparatively, Lane County saw an increase of **19,624 jobs**, a Local Growth Rate of **11%**. This data reveals that employment in Lane County is growing at a lower rate than national employment.

Largest Employment Sectors

The following data looks at how employment growth breaks down by industry. Table 3³ shows a selection of four different employment sectors in Lane County. This selection is exemplary of areas where there are opportunities for growth as well as areas that are declining. Additionally, these four industries: manufacturing, retail trade, educational services and healthcare and social assistance, have the potential to inform economic development as they exhibit areas where

a qualitative shift in resources may prove beneficial. More context for how to interpret these numbers will follow in Tables 4-6.

In Lane County, the manufacturing industry lost **5,772 jobs** between 2001 and 2016. Nationally, manufacturing also experienced decline with **3,817,900 jobs** lost over the same time period. In Lane County specifically, the retail trade industry was a huge employer and projected immense growth rates only to tank in January of 2008.¹⁵ The **-27.4%** change in the manufacturing industry means many people were left unemployed. The other four industries experienced varying degrees of growth, with retail trade on the lower end of the overall percentage change at **10.2%** and educational services on the high end with **80.9%** change. Though these percentages can seem impressive, it is also important to look at the aggregate numbers; not all of the industries that experience high percentage change actually create that many more jobs. Take health care and social assistance for example, which grew by **8,116 jobs** between 2001 to 2016 an overall percent change of **39.9% in Lane County**.⁴

Shift-share Analysis

Table 4 shows how County rates compare to the National numbers. A shift-share analysis looks at the National Growth Rate and compares

⁴ See Table 3 in the Appendix

³ See Table 3 in the Appendix

that to industry specific growth locally (Industrial Mix Component). The third element of a shift-share analysis is the Competitive Share Analysis, which provides some information on industry competitiveness.

TABLE 4. SHIFT SHARE ANALYSIS – UNITED STATES AND LANE COUNTY, 2001-2016

Industry	National Growth Rate Component	Industrial Mix Component	Competitive Share Component
Manufacturing	3,577.0	-8320.7	-1026.7
Retail Trade	3,767.2	-2392.9	893.7
Educational Services	396.8	925.0	566.3
Health Care and Social Assistance	3460.0	5467.8	-811.8

Source: NAICS

Accordingly, manufacturing lost a higher percentage of jobs in Lane County than the National growth rate and is therefore not a very competitive industry. Whereas, educational services are growing much faster than the national growth rate and are relatively competitive. The shift-share analysis provides a good overall summary of which industries are gaining and losing employment. However, further analysis is necessary to draw more precise conclusions. Tables 5 and 6 look at location quotient and population-employment ratios to help determine where Lane County has economic potential.

Employment Factors by Location

Location quotient is a measure that shows the relative concentration of employment in a given area. Higher concentrations of employment are reflected by a location quotient (LQ) greater than 1, lower concentrations of employment have an LQ less than 1. Table 6 breaks down LQ by industry.

An important factor when looking at location quotient is to not interpret these numbers arbitrarily. Sometimes, a high (greater than 1) LQ can

signify an important industry that may require attention or an important growth industry, whereas, a low (less than 1) LQ could be interpreted as an industry of little promise or an industry with potential for emergence. It is important to consider all of the data previously presented in conjunction with one another for the most efficacious interpretations of where economic growth is in Lane County. For example, manufacturing has a high LQ, however, as we see in Table 5⁵ there has been a decline in overall employment growth.

Employment Factors by Population

The last factor to take into account is the Population/Employment ratio (P/E ratio). These ratios reflect the portion of the population that is participating in the labor force. In other words, the P/E ratio measures the number of people per job in a particular industry in a given location. The P/E ratio can also help in making inter-community comparisons of different sectors. For the purposes of this analysis, the P/E ratio aids in understanding the jobs/people balance for four industries across three geographies.

Combining the Population/Employment Ratio into this analysis adds yet another layer of trends to interpret. Although, as identified from Table 6, educational services have the potential for expansion, there is already an imbalance of jobs/people.⁶ That said, the ratio has declined since 2001 which shows promise. Looking across geographic regions, the ratio is still higher in Lane County than in the State of Oregon or in the nation, which is something to consider if you are thinking of moving to Eugene to work in education. Healthcare and social assistance is another economic sector that presents a favorable P/E ratio. The ratio has declined over time reflecting more demand and availability for this kind of labor, and in Lane County, this sector had the most growth in jobs between 2001-2016.

⁶ See Table 6 in the Appendix

⁵ See Table 5 in the Appendix

Economic Implications

Though this community economic analysis does not look at employment in the River Road area it does lend some insight into the overall community context. The data indicates that employment in Lane County is growing overall; however, the poverty rate in our study area is still **19.3%**.⁷ This implies that the current economic conditions in the community are not ones that are lifting people out of poverty. It is important to ask what policies make sense at the neighborhood level to address income inequality and lack of employment.

Proposing transit development along the River Road Corridor is an option that should be pursued. Connecting the River Road community to other parts of the surrounding areas has the potential to impact the economic characteristics of this site in a positive way; more transportation leads to more access, more access leads to more influx of opportunity and industry, more influx leads to more jobs. Now, with the existing transit infrastructure, it would take someone in the River Road about an hour to get to the nearest hospital using public transportation. Not only is this disconcerting in terms of medical response time, but also, if you are someone who works in the emerging health care and social assistance industry, and do not have access to personal transportation, you would have a commute of at least 2 hours every day. Not having reliable and accessible transportation is a barrier to economic development. Considering the River Road area for corridor development opens up the possibilities for more industry to move into this area. In conclusion, as we collaborated on proposed alternatives and plans for development it was important to keep these economic characteristics in mind and think of what options can be pursued in the short and long term.

EmX Bus Service in West Eugene

Source: Lane Transit District (2019)

Transit Investment and Equity

Source: Metro Magazine (2019)

⁷ See Figure 9 in the Appendix

Housing Trends

As of 2018, Eugene has an estimated population of 171,245 residents, including 22,760 students enrolled at the University of Oregon.^{16,17} Population forecasts indicate that the city is growing, with a projected annual population growth of 1% resulting in 34,000 new residents between 2012-2032. Consequently, the city has reported an estimated housing need of 15,105 new homes by 2032.¹⁸

For the purposes of this report, housing trends and characteristics are assessed for Oregon, Lane County, Eugene, and Old Station. Insights gained from the following analysis are intended to inform evaluation criteria and aid in decision making processes for future planning purposes for the Old Station study area.

Old Station's home ownership rates are decreasing.

In comparing housing tenure trends for Oregon, Lane County, Eugene, and Old Station, all areas show a decrease in homeownership.⁸ Upon closer inspection, it is apparent that Old Station has an overall higher percentage of owner-occupied households than the general trend indicated for the city. However, the percentage of owner-occupied households has decreased slightly between 2010 to 2017 for all four geographies, and Old Station shows the greatest change with 3.4% decrease of owner-occupied status.

Old Station has high housing costs

Housing value-to-income ratio reflects the number of years it would take to purchase a home at a given price relative to the buyer's median household income. A general guideline reflecting housing affordability purchase for home-buyers is a ratio of approximately 2.6 years of income respective to the housing price.¹⁹ Ratios for 2017 are highest for Eugene, at 5.9 (with Oregon close behind at 5.7; Table 7).

TABLE 7. HOUSING VALUE - OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Geographies	2010	2017
Oregon	5.4	5.7
Lane County	5.6	5.4
Eugene	6.2	5.9
Census Tract 28	5.0	4.5

Sources:

ACS 2006-2010 (5-Year Estimates), Tables S1901 & S2506

ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Table S1901 & S2507

This indicates that, given the median household value and median household income for the area, it would take 5.9 years of household income to purchase a home. With a rent-to-income ratio of 4.5, Old Station ranks lowest for the four geographies, but still reflects unaffordable housing costs, requiring 4.5 years of income to purchase the average cost of a home in the area.

Old Station has a strong demand for rental units

A 2019 economic analysis conducted by ECONorthwest reveals that rental units encompass 37% of the area's single-family dwellings in the River Road/Santa Clara area.¹⁸ Old Station mirrors area trends with 39.5% of single-family dwellings existing as rental units.²⁰ General trends indicate that the cost to buy a house has not kept pace with income levels for all geographies in Oregon (Table 8). Old Station shows the greatest change between 2010 to 2017, with a 6.3% increase in rent paid relative to income for households (Table 8). State trends for Oregon are similar (6.1% increase), while Lane County and Eugene have fared better at 4.4% and 3.9%, respectively. This indicates that while median income and median rent have both increased for all regions, Oregon and Old Station lag behind Lane County and Eugene when it comes to median income keeping pace

⁸ see Figure 10 in Appendix

with median rent increases.⁹ Consequently, it has become less affordable to own a home and more appealing to rent in these areas.

TABLE 8. RENT-TO-INCOME RATIO - OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Geography	2010	2017
Oregon	17%	23%
Lane County	19%	24%
Eugene	20%	24%
Census Tract 28	19%	25%

Sources:

ACS 2006-2010 (5-Year Estimates), Tables S1901 and B25063

ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Tables S1901 and B25063

Nearly 40% of Old Station residents are cost burdened

Cost-burdened households are defined as residents paying 30% or more of their income on housing costs.²¹ In looking at trends across the four geographies, it is clear that Old Station has lower rates of cost burden than Eugene.¹⁰ For 2017, approximately 38.7% of Old Station residents struggled to afford their housing costs. While Old Station has lower rates of cost burden than the other regions overall, it demonstrates the greatest growth in cost burdened households at 3.7% growth between 2010-2017.¹¹

Demand for New Housing & Multifamily Units

Analyzing these trends, it is clear that more affordable housing is needed in the River Road neighborhood and Old Station area. With little buildable land left in the Old Station area this demand will increasingly be met with multi-family units of apartments, row houses and townhomes. Additionally the passage of H.B. 2001 should encourage developments of new duplexes, triplexes, and fourplexes in the area as well as accessory dwelling units.²² It is clear that the area is essentially built out in terms of subdivisions and therefore the future of housing for River Road will be focused on infill development

⁹ see Table 9 in the Appendix

¹⁰ see Figure 10 in Appendix

and multifamily units. This development is sorely needed as only 10% of the housing stock in the River Road neighborhood is made up of multifamily units, compared to 36% for the City of Eugene.²³

These are the exact types of structures we are proposing for our site and they will help fill a pressing community need for a wider variety of affordable housing types. Our first proposed structure at the former Old Station on the Northeast corner of River Road and River Avenue fits the bill perfectly. Taking advantage of the existing C-2 Community Commercial zoning, it is a 6 story, mixed-use building with ground floor retail and social services. The remaining five floors will feature mixed income housing with 20% inclusionary zoning for affordable housing. This will provide 16 new affordable housing units for the neighborhood. We intend to replicate this formula for mixed-use structures on the remaining three corners creating a minimum of 50 new affordable housing units. This will help meet the increasing demand for rental units in the River Road neighborhood driven by the rising cost of home ownership in the area and Eugene at large.

Eugene, Oregon

Source: Lauram12345 (2006)

¹¹ see Figure 11 in Appendix

Housing Implications

The housing trends above surrounding affordability, ability and preference to rent or own, and housing availability impact the current and future residents of Old Station. With almost 40% of households in Old Station being cost-burdened in 2017, there is a clear need for additional affordable housing in the neighborhood. As part of our site analysis above, we found that there is already some affordable multi-family housing in the area, but not enough to support all residents in a way that would reduce cost-burden for all residents. The neighborhood in Old Station is comprised predominantly of lower-income households with a high percent of cost burdened households. This indicates that affordable housing is needed in this community. The percent of people renting is increasing in this area, which may mean it is too expensive to purchase housing in the area. There is a lack of supply of purchasable housing, or people are only expecting to live in the neighborhood temporarily; thus, renting instead of owning a home. The rent-to-income ratio in this area is also higher than statewide data, at 25.1% in 2017 according to Table 8. This shows that on average, households are paying 25.1% of income on rental expenses. When compared with Eugene, Old Station has a high rent-to-income ratio for its residents who have lower income overall. These are important statistics to understand as we recommend land-use and development options for the area. Old Station's strong need for rental properties is influenced by the demographics of the area and the affordability of purchasable homes.

The need for multi-family housing in the area can be fulfilled by developing on the C-2 zoned land on the four corners of River Road and River Avenue, with the expectation that over the long-term, this

will expand further along the corridor and in the neighborhood. With clear need for multi-family, affordable housing, and little supply currently available in the neighborhood, it will be important to provide this for future residents as the population continues to increase at a higher rate than the city as a whole. In addition, rental units are in demand due to the high cost to purchase and lifestyle change of the overall population, so providing this multi-family housing in the form of rental properties will cater to the needs of the local community.

The Oaks at 14th –
Low Income Apartments in Eugene, Oregon

Source: Affordable Housing Online (2019)

Team Process & Methods

Our team process began with establishing roles and expectations as we began to understand the entirety of the project and each individual member's strengths in the research, development, and execution process. Once established, we created an outline of expectations. The key elements, other than the vast research on city plans, community socioeconomic information, and feedback from our instructors, was the site visit and the design charette. The site visit allowed us to visualize the neighborhood and understand what we had to work with on a deeper contextual level than just looking at maps and reading about the area. The design charette was one of the first times we were able to put all of our ideas on paper and begin to see how it would all take shape. Through this exercise, we learned that we had many strong ideas, but were concentrating them in one small area, when in reality, we needed to expand our scope and include our recommendation along River Road and into the neighborhoods. We realized that the focus of our project is not on a single parcel of land, but rather a catalyst site intended to spur a new functionality of the existing area (e.g., between the riverfront neighborhood and the North Eugene Highschool).

As a result, we adapted our vision so that it is both modest and monumental – a plan aimed to provide the user with not only public and private spaces but also with special “places” that set the stage for a sociable scenario of all socioeconomic groups. Our highest priority is to enhance pedestrian safety, provide low cost housing, increase neighborhood vibrancy, and to attract more families and businesses into the neighborhood. Ideally, our proposals for the redesign of Old Station can maximize the opportunities of the area to meet the needs of new and current residents and enhance the standard of living. Consequently, we anticipate that the implementation of our vision will take about twenty years.

Source: Kaarin Knudson (2019)

Source: Kaarin Knudson (2019)

Overview of Concept Plan

Vision

We envision the Four Corners of River Road as a vibrant, mixed-use transit-oriented development that is safe, walkable and sustainable. This vision is formed by the question, “Where do we want to go together?” We recognize that the River Road community is at a critical turning point in its history. The massive investment and changes coming with LTD’s EmX corridor expansion will forever change the neighborhood and it offers the opportunity to introduce further changes for the community’s future. To that end we propose new transit-oriented development (TOD) along the corridor combining mixed-use development in public-private partnerships to create new businesses, affordable housing and community gathering spaces built to the highest environmental standards. We advocate for a complete streets approach with improved bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure at these new developments in order to transform the neighborhood from an auto-dependent suburb to a thriving community that is vibrant, safe, walkable and sustainable.

Guiding Principles

Our vision seeks to create a 20-minute neighborhood tying the people of Old Station to their homes, resulting in a walkable, forward-looking, inclusive community. Our proposal seeks to achieve this by creating a pedestrian-friendly neighborhood with dense residential development along the River Road corridor. In order to accomplish our vision for Old Station, we are guided by the principles of improving:

- Placemaking: neighborhood character & vibrancy
- Mixed-use: multi-family, affordable housing
- Accessibility: pedestrian and cyclist safety
- Connectivity: people, places, ideas

Strategy

The Four Corners of River Road has the ability to transform the overall vibrancy of the neighborhood over the next 20 years by:

More specifically, by following the five stages of TOD, we can incorporate all the elements in our action plan for the community (Figure 12).

1. Assess: How ready is Old Station for the TOD and is there a need for it?
2. Enable: Making policies that can be helpful in implementing the design strategies
3. Plan and Design: How cities are being designed and how they will impact the future of transit
4. Implement: Making the change actually happen
5. Economic Influence: After the implementation we have to observe how the new project has impacted the overall economic condition of the city.

- Improving accessibility and connectivity for local residents to nearby transit stations, local businesses, community spaces and schools
- Providing safe transit lanes for all modes of transportation
- Implementing the EmX enhanced stop near retail business and services to instill a sense of place and culture in the neighborhood
- Creating placemaking elements to the neighborhood while maintaining the neighborhood’s culture in terms of urban planning and design
- Supply housing for the “missing middle” to ensure Envision Eugene and Neighborhood Plan goals are met over the next 20 years

Desian Concepts

Accessibility and Connectivity

Neighborhood planning collaboration processes have highlighted the community's concerns around safety and multi-modal improvements.²⁵ Current transportation infrastructure along the River Road corridor includes a four-lane road with a center turn lane. Bike lanes and sidewalks exist on both sides and transit service runs up and down the road. According to LTD staff, there are an estimated 2,500 riders per day using the LTD transit services.²⁶ As LTD seeks to expand services along the River Road corridor, the implementation of a Bus Rapid Transit system (locally referred to as the EmX) will result in increased frequency of bus services, with service occurring every 15 minutes along the corridor.²⁶ However, there are key design considerations to consider to help transit succeed and improve the safety and accessibility of the area.

The Arlington TOD case study made substantial accessibility improvements along their corridor, and thereby offer some useful design concepts for Old Station to consider adopting. Arlington recognized early on the need to implement multimodal transportation planning to offer a variety of travel choices to community members and make car travel unnecessary. That said, pedestrian environment in the TOD project was initially neglected.²⁷

County planners and residents began showing an increased interest in pedestrian and cyclist accessibility in the early 2000s. Since then, the creation of guidelines for pedestrian and streetscape design standards has helped the county make significant strides in accessibility. The mitigation of pedestrian hazards has been addressed through the implementation of wider sidewalks, curb ramps, and improved street lighting. Cyclists benefit from greater connectivity from the transit station corridor to the greater bike trail

system in the surrounding area. This provides increased safety for cyclists and enhanced recreational opportunities. Bridges have also been adapted to better serve pedestrians and cyclists, and residential areas have received street resurfacing improvements and bike lane additions.²⁷ Bicyclists are also able to find adequate parking along the corridor as site plan reviews for TOD projects stipulate the provision of secure indoor bicycle parking as a requirement.

To address traffic congestion, Arlington implemented a transportation demand management (TDM) initiative in 1989. TDM reflects strategies utilized to reduce travel demand in an area.²⁸ Arlington's TDM is geared towards addressing workplace commuter trips and seeks to influence travel behavior through lessening single-occupancy trips during peak-hour traffic. and involves a variety of actors, including employers, residents, transit users, and developers among other people.²⁷ The TDM implementation has been continuously refined over the past fifty years and led to the creation of the Arlington Transportation Partners Program, which offers employer program assistance. A 2000 survey on Arlington's TDM outcomes showed an overall 10% reduction in single-occupancy trips.²⁷ Car ownership along the metro corridor is also significantly less than the national average. A 2012 car ownership survey showed that 16.7% of corridor residents have zero cars compared to 9% nationally.²⁶

A reduced need for parking emerged a byproduct of the county's focus on minimizing automobile use, undertaking community mixed-use development near the five stations, and increasing pedestrian and cyclist accessibility.²⁸ Average metro ridership has grown substantially along with corridor, from 13,637 daily riders in 1991 to 33,891 in 2010 nationally.²⁸ A 2012 commuting behavior survey showed that 42.8% used transit to commute to work, 9.5 percent walk or bike, and 3.1 percent work from home.²⁹ Further trends show that for those who use

the metro transit in the corridor, 76.9% prefer to walk, 6.3% take another bus, and only 10.9% use auto.³⁰ As a result, the area has generated less traffic and the county has been able to reduce parking requirements for development.^{27, 32}

Accessibility and Connectivity Lessons – Design Strategies for Old Station

Old Station should also take note of Arlington’s significant progress towards enhanced accessibility. Arlington’s case study demonstrates that prioritizing a pedestrian and cyclist-friendly environment delivers results. Improvements such as widened sidewalks, improved street lighting, and greater bike trail connectivity encouraged residents to utilize alternate modes of transit. Average daily metro ridership showed a net gain of 20,254 riders over a 19-year period. This helped gradually reduce parking in a dense urban environment and led to relatively little increases in traffic.

Sidewalk Zones

Source: National Association of City Transportation Officials (2019)

Source: National Association of City Transportation Officials (2019)

The following strategies can help LTD achieve its goals of improving transit safety and accessibility for the area’s residents:

- Create guidelines for pedestrian and streetscape design standards
- Implement wider sidewalks, curb ramps, and improve street lighting
- Connect the transit station corridor to the greater bike trail system in the surrounding area
- Implement protected bicycle lanes along River Road
- Provide secure indoor bicycle parking as a requirement for new development proposals
- Adapt bridges to better serve pedestrians and cyclists
- Resurface streets and add bike lanes in residential areas
- Implement a transportation demand management initiative

Mixed-use buildings/multi-family housing

Our proposal includes redevelopment of current underutilized commercial space on the corners of this intersection. In order to stay within current zoning code, we propose to build mixed-use buildings on the community commercial land on our site. This will allow us to develop taller buildings, with commercial and retail spaces on the first floor and residential, mixed-use rental units on the remaining floors. Community commercial zoning limits building size to a maximum of 120 feet with medium density buildings ranging from 85-95 feet.³³ This is an approximate maximum height of 8 stories for high-density buildings and 5-6 stories for medium-density buildings. These developments will happen in stages as explained below in the Implementation section the buildings lining River Road will transform into a mix of medium- and high-density to accommodate for population growth, housing needs, and the shift to a TOD. We understand that not all of the residential dwellings will be low-income, but we want to stress the importance of affordability for current and future residents as we navigate the housing issue in Eugene.

Each corner of River Road and River Avenue features outdated infrastructure, old shopping centers, and large parking lots that are never filled completely. With a growing population in the neighborhood, and a need for low-income housing based on the demographics of the area, affordable, multi-family housing is a viable option to be included in our vision for the neighborhood. The vision for this neighborhood on River Road can be similar to the Dedham, MA vision, as explained in the below case study, as goals and the current infrastructure are similar. A mixed-use building with retail shops on the first floor and housing on the top floors would be viable at this intersection. A preference towards utilizing local experts to aid in the planning process is present in this area as the neighborhood wants to keep its culture intact.

Crescent Village Apartments in Eugene, Oregon

Source: Crescent Village (2019)

Amazon Corner Apartments in Eugene, Oregon

Source: Dan Straub (2019)

Case Study: Dior Dedham

The neighborhood surrounding the intersection of River Road and River Avenue is overpowered by strip malls and fast food restaurants with large parking lots, contributing to the sprawl that is common in these suburban areas. Large parking lots support these shopping centers, but also end up creating empty space that could be utilized differently. Many neighborhoods in suburban areas across the U.S have similar strip centers and shopping centers that were once wanted by the community and now have outdated designs and diminishing use. The concept of retrofitting strip malls and shopping centers is becoming more popular and many cities have found that these updates contributed positively to the local community, providing multi-story, mixed-use buildings in place of one-story big box stores, and updating the urban design of the area, among other benefits. A strong example of this retrofitting phenomenon is that of the strip mall in Dedham, MA. Around 2015, Boston's Regional Planning Agency (RPA) and the Metropolitan Area Planning Council (MAPC) worked on comprehensive plans for the area at the same time the owner of the Dedham strip center, Chris Priore, started considering the future of the land he owned. Their plans worked in tandem to provide a positive outcome for community members and for the city's vitality.³⁴

Dedham, MA, a suburb of about 25,000 residents southwest of Boston, is the home of the Legacy Place shopping mall, opened in 2009, which is adjacent to the future Dior Dedham mixed-use building, a Whole Foods grocer, existing affordable apartments, and the area's commuter rail station. What is now the Dior Dedham center, a 0.8-acre parcel of land previously had retail shops on the main frontage, a larger building containing Priore's family-owned Dedham Cabinet Shop, and a parking lot to accommodate shoppers. This strip center is located along the Providence Highway, a busy 6-lane road that makes the area conducive for automobile transit but not pedestrian or cycle transit. Priore recognized the flaws with this suburban sprawl and sought to improve the strip center for the surrounding residents.³⁴

The MAPC and the RPA noticed the connectivity flaws with the entire neighborhood and conducted two studies on the city to see how they could improve the area in terms of urban design, housing, and connectivity to the retail centers and rail station. While these studies were being conducted, the city of Dedham also contracted the Urban Land Institute (ULI) Technical Assistance Panel (TAP) to provide insight from a broad range of industry experts (architects, engineers, planners, etc.) on land use improvements. At the same time, Priore's cabinet shop was expanding and needed to relocate to a larger store, so he was open to completely redesigning the infrastructure on the land. He utilized the feedback and findings from TAP to ultimately make his decision on how to redevelop to optimize the available space while considering the impact on the local community.³⁴ Priore had ideas for the redevelopment that were confirmed by attending the TAP, solidifying his plans of building a mixed-use structure with retail shops on the first floor and multi-family housing on the top floors. Because of the housing need in the area, he aimed to provide some housing relief with his development.³⁴

Priore worked with a local architect on the development and used a local attorney to aid as needed with the legal process. The city planners supported his vision for the area and provided support where needed to ensure pedestrian connectivity was improved, and open spaces were being utilized to benefit the community. The planning process was smooth for the most part as there was very little community opposition to the development. They were able to proceed with construction on a normal timeline, barring the issue of securing financing. Because Priore was not a developer by trade, he did not have an adequate down-payment for his construction loan and had to find a capital partner before taking out the loan and beginning construction. Priore set out to develop a multi-family housing structure in a mixed-use building with a contemporary design that matched the Legacy Place building design as opposed to using a more traditional New England design style common in the Boston area. Figure 13 shows the design of the new mixed-use Dior Dedham building. Everything they set out to do was accomplished and Priore achieved

his goals of increasing multi-family housing while contributing to the MAPC's broader goals for the city of connectivity and improved urban design.³⁴

Ellen Dunham-Jones, an expert on retrofitting suburbia believes that shopping malls and strip centers across the U.S. are heading towards revitalization and sustainable redevelopment as large retail stores are becoming less desirable for consumers.³⁴ According to the American Planning Association, nationally, large retailers and shopping centers are seeing a shift in how buyers interact with them. In some cases, storefronts are closing due in large part to the online retail presence and the overall shift in consumer buying patterns.³⁵ With empty storefronts in large shopping centers or outdated strip malls, cities need a way to revitalize the areas and create resiliency in this transformative time.³⁵ Revitalizing these areas can add vibrancy and open spaces to areas that were once bland, spread out retail centers. Dunham-Jones describes the dynamic of underperforming asphalt, common in suburban areas and how it can be retrofitted into a more usable open space or development opportunity. Underperforming asphalt is a term used by developers to describe underutilized parking lots.³⁵ Underperforming asphalt was a factor Priore encountered and helped influence the decision to rethink its land use.³⁴ Recreating the open space on parking lots as well as redeveloping on retail shops provides an innovative way to make public spaces more accessible.

There are many aspects of the Dior Dedham project that relate to our River Road project. Neighborhood plans in our area can take key aspects from the Dedham case to revitalize the area and create a space the community needs and wants. As with Dior Dedham the elements outlined below can be improved for Old Station.

The Dior Dedham development project included positive implementation elements that would translate well to the Old Station revitalization:

Implementation support

- The use of local experts (planners, architects, attorneys, capital partners)
- Engagement and support from the local community
- Support from the land owner to transform the built environment on the strip mall

Development ideas

- Updating urban design of the built environment
- Adding multi-family housing in the form of mixed-use buildings

Mixed-use Building – Dior Dedham

Source: Dior Dedham (2019)

Low Cost Housing

Low-cost mixed-use housing is one in which we reduce the cost of construction without sacrificing the strength required for the performance of the building. When production is low cost, we are able to provide the housing at below market cost so residents in the Old Station neighbor can afford them and are less cost burdened by housing expenses. Sustainable mixed use should ensure a better quality of life for current and future generations. It should combine protection of the **environment, sensible use of natural resources, economic growth and social progress.**

People earning low to moderate incomes are increasing in numbers and unable to access housing that is affordable, hence demand for low-cost mixed-use housing far exceeds its supply. As discussed above in the housing trends and implications, there is evident demand for affordable housing based on income levels and number of families below the poverty line. There is a need for the adoption of strong durable environmentally friendly, ecologically appropriate, energy efficient and yet cost-effective materials and appropriate technologies in construction. Sustainable technology when adopted with care and creativity, can lead to a unique architectural expression.

Why do we need low-cost mixed-use housing?

There are a number of factors that influence the demand for affordable housing.

Low-cost mixed-use housing is beneficial to a community in many ways, including:

- Stronger labor force:
 - A good supply of housing for all income groups helps a community retain jobs and retail stores, and helps business owners attract and retain good workers.
 - Employees are able to live near employment centers, so are more able to report to work on time and have time to improve their job skills or get an education.

- Economic benefits:
 - New construction and management of a property creates new employment and generates multiple ripple effects that strengthen the local economy.
- Stronger families:
 - Affordable housing creates a more stable environment for children; children do better in school. Families are able to save for a home purchase down payment.

Approach for low cost housing

- There should be a logical approach for providing appropriate technology based on the availability of options, considering its technical and economic analysis.
- There should be optimal space in the design considering efficiency of space, minimum circulation space.
- Economy should be considered in the design of individual buildings, layouts, clusters etc.
- While preparing the specifications it should be kept in mind that, cost effective construction systems are adopted.

- Energy efficiency has gained considerable importance due to energy crisis especially in developing countries. Orientation, built-form, openings & materials play a vital role besides landscaping / outdoor environment.
- To develop an effective mechanism for providing appropriate technology-based shelter particularly to the vulnerable group and economically weaker section

Factors affecting construction cost estimation

- Building cost: the building cost can be divided into two
- building material cost: 65-70 %
- labor cost: 30-35 %
- Size: the smaller the project in terms of scope or the number of square feet, the more it will cost per square feet.
- Type: different types of projects have different levels of complexity and detail.
- Special construction: complexity can greatly increase the cost of project.
- Project accessibility
- Labor rates
- Material cost
- General economic pressure

Techniques and material help us reduce cost of the building

Recycling

- Recycled materials adapted for low cost housing include wood and rubber that are previously been used.
- Reprocessed into materials that are used in building walls and other parts of a house
- Recycled glass and metal are also used on occasions
- These recycled materials are often less expensive than using fully natural products.

Extensive Planning

- In extensive planning the more planning goes into the house, the less the actual construction will cost
- Contractors should plan out exact dimensions and should gather facts
- Contractors should look for best material at the cheapest prices so they can order exactly what they need
- This saves up money that would otherwise be wasted on unnecessary supplies and cleanup caused by littered materials.
- Most houses are built as quickly as possible without this detailed planning beforehand

Modular Planning

- Modular, or prefabricated design is a type of construction where pieces of the house or typically whole rooms or major parts, are built off site in large factories
- The process allows them to be built efficiently and exactly according to the building standards
- At the site the pieces are connected to the house
- Since material are assembled on site the owner saves money on construction time
- Many of these processes use newer technologies such as SIPs (structurally integrated panels), creating stronger, better insulated structures and shortened construction timelines.

Infilling

- Infilling is the practice of going back through residential areas and building in areas that had previously been left empty.
- Infilling makes better use of existing space
- It is less expensive for contractors overall.

Placemaking

Communal Place Making

We all desire a place we can call home. There are many elements that can make a place feel like home such as tradition, religion, art, culture, and landscape. These all play a vital role in creating a place and giving it a sense of identity. Well placed elements such as public art, fountains, courtyards and other community gathering spaces can imbue this sense of home and community.

Placemaking can be achieved by creating a sense of belonging which can be accomplished through community engagement and well-structured policies. The places that we live in and the experience of our everyday life gives people this sense of “home.” Giving an identity to a certain community or place creates more significance for residents and helps them to take ownership of their space. Creating spaces for people to gather is a good first step in placemaking, which can be complemented by community programs designed to create social interaction between people belonging to different age groups, socioeconomic backgrounds and racial groups.

Downtown Eugene

Source: City of Eugene (2019)

Objectives for Placemaking Elements

- Create a center that provides community programs and opportunities for empowerment and growth.
- Architecture that enhances the local neighborhood and its culture.
- Engage the community with cultural programs
- Increase interaction between the community center users in order to remove stigma and create a feeling of mutual acceptance and empowerment
- Keep connectivity a vital part of design
- Design a facility that user may identify as “home”
- Encourage new businesses to provide economic opportunity.

Mural by Hush – 20x21 EUG Mural Project

Source: City of Eugene (2018)

Efficient and Integrated Design

The following design considerations should also be kept in mind for the project:

Introverted Planning: Instead of opening up to the outside world, rather the design opens up inside the building/ project (Figure 14).

FIGURE 14. INTROVERTED PLANNING

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

Outdoor Spaces: They can be functional or nonfunctional depending on the design and the program but we can see that there are many advantages of the courtyard and how it is incorporated in the design (Figure 15).

FIGURE 15. OUTDOOR SPACES

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

Tree planting, reduced parking spaces, public art and sculptures also offer a number of advantages, including:

- Rediscovering history and heritage
- An interactive experience creating human connections
- Creating an oasis or a breathing space within the city
- A space for remembrance and reflection

Open Spaces and Recreation

We propose a variety of open spaces to be included in the development for the purpose of outdoor recreation. Outdoor recreation is a vital component of community life and a major industry here in the Pacific Northwest. We propose the following outdoor recreation spaces for the Four Corners of River Road:

- Public plaza with placemaking water feature.
- Large public mural designed by local artists featuring the history of River Road and the local high school mascot, the Highlanders.
- Several pocket parks incorporated into the design of residential structures on site for residential use.
- A public playground with multiple sections for age appropriate play and safety.
- A bicycle share station.
- A dockless e-scooter sharing station.
- Generous allocation of park benches.
- A community garden.
- 20 sets of tables and chairs to be dispersed in various locations on site.
- Raised planters to serve as landscaping and green screening.
- A small public amphitheater for community events and plays.
- Sections of parking lots dedicated for weekend markets and food truck use during special events.

Sustainability

As we enter a new decade in the 2020's the growing threat of climate change to our way of life is greater than ever before. By implementing proven sustainability solutions and focusing on the triple bottom line the Four Corners of River Road can be an environmentally friendly site that promotes a greener lifestyle for its residents and remains financially viable for decades to come. To that end we propose the following sustainability solutions for the development.

- Strict energy use guidelines for new buildings
- A complete streets approach with large urban tree canopy to promote walkability, shade buildings, absorb rainwater and emissions.
- Sustainable transportation options on site like bicycle share and e-scooter stations.
- Pursuing LEED certification for buildings on site larger than 30,000 sf.
- A new city ordinance requiring cool roofs or green roofs on structures larger than 20,000 square feet (i.e., similar to the City of Portland³⁶).
- Public-private partnerships to offer incentives for onsite renewable energy such as solar photovoltaic panels.
- Extensive stormwater management through the use of rainwater catchment systems, rain gardens, and bioswales where appropriate.
- Landscaped pocket parks serving as an urban oasis for residents.
- Native vegetation for landscaping and a community garden where residents can grow their own food for consumption or sale

Mixed-use Food and Community Hub in Eugene (Green Building)

Source: Essex General Construction – Mahonia Building (2019)

Multi-family Housing in Eugene (LEED Gold Targeted)

Source: Essex General Construction – 35 Club Road (2019)

Source: Aqsa Khan (2019)

Funding Toolkit

Public and Private Partnerships

One concern our team has had when thinking about our River Road site is financing. The Old Station is currently designated as a park and ride with three different bus stops. The station is just South of a major freeway, located on the busiest intersection on River Road, difficult to access by vehicle and shares the lot with a vacant building. Our vision for this site is for it to be redeveloped for mixed use affordable housing and begin to function as a community gathering space which will later catalyze the other three street corners to develop and evolve. We are committed to development that prioritizes affordability, walkability, pedestrian and bike safety, local businesses, neighborhood branding and community development. Our team acknowledges that these are lofty and long-term visions and are also strategizing to propose recommendations that will appeal to the local transit authority.

Looking at other case studies of similar redevelopment lends insight into innovative funding schemes. One Santa Fe, based in Los Angeles, offers an interesting case study in respects to public-private partnerships and innovative financing; an important reference for our site. To begin, the land where One Santa Fe was built is still owned by LA Metro and thus, benefits Metro in several ways. First, the terms of the lease are for 81 years, “with a base rent set at \$525,150, plus a percentage of commercial rent, and a schedule of increases greater than the consumer price index.”³⁷ These leasing terms ensure revenue that Metro can later invest in future projects. After the lease agreement expires, Metro retained the right to revert the site to its original use, so, for a site that was not previously being used and can change uses in the future, Metro made an advantageous choice. Additionally, Metro rents part of the commercial space at One Santa Fe at a prorated fee, and through their public-private partnership they are thinking of ways to open new rail stations that service the area. This approach to public-private partnership and leasing agreements is

something our team should keep in mind when pitching development plans to Lane Transit District (LTD).

FIGURE 16. FUNDING TOOLKIT

Public-Private Partnership

Source: Hayley Shapiro (2019)

A simplified version of what a revenue stream could look like if LTD chose to lease the land and establish Public-Private Partnerships is in Figure 16 shown here. As the leasing entity, LTD will not benefit unless the private developers find a way to build the project, therefore this chart also outlines some funding opportunities for private developers. Following the example of the One Santa Fe case, this chart breaks developers up into two categories: Residential and Commercial; categorizing rental revenue similarly. Where the funding

comes from, will inform how the lease will need to be drawn up. In the case of One Santa Fe, different entities owned the different aspects of the building: affordable housing, market-rate housing and commercial. This subdivision permitted developers to look for funding from various sources. Loans for affordable housing came primarily from HUD and funding for the ground floor commercial portion of the project came from Section 108 loans through a program that allows cities to loan federal Community Development Block Grant funds. This innovative funding scheme is certainly involved, but it creates an enticing paradigm where public and private organizations work together on development projects. Additionally, it leaves the leasing entity, which in our case would be LTD, in a position where it is involved in the TOD on the River Road Corridor as well as earning profit from private rent.

One Santa Fe found funding from many different sources including: multifamily mortgage revenue bonds, HUD, LA's city housing trust fund, and community development block grant funds. A funding package like this had requisites. Developers of One Santa Fe had to adhere to a variety of different stipulations for affordable housing and deliver these outcomes in the final project. Our vision for the Old Station is that a portion of the multi-use building on the catalyst site will offer affordable housing. If private developers look to federal or state sources of funding for this project the affordable housing component will most likely be mandatory.

Luckily, in the case of One Santa Fe, the developers did not see the affordability requirements as constraints, but as opportunities. Also, it is important to keep in mind that One Santa Fe was entering a part of the Arts District that was once an artist haven where studios only cost about \$150 a month. So, regardless of the fact that the developers were including affordable housing, the community still had concerns about such a large development coming to their artsy and industrious part of town. Currently, 20% of the units in One Santa Fe are considered affordable. The mortgage revenue bonds mandated that 20 percent of the units set aside as affordable had to be at 50% of the area median income (AMI).³⁸ The loan from the city's housing trust

fund also required lower rents on the affordable units at 40 percent AMI. Not to mention the myriad of qualifications set forth by HUD, which required significant attention from the developers. Nonetheless, both the developers and HUD were enthusiastic about building a project of this scale and scope and pointing to it as an example of what a HUD project could look like. Adhering to these affordability requirements meant net operating income of the project was impacted significantly, but developers knew that these sacrifices needed to be made in order to get the project built.

In proposing our vision to LTD, we wanted to suggest alternatives to auctioning or selling the land outright. The Old Station has the potential to serve as a catalyst site in this area, and as we continue to ask throughout this project, "where do we want to go together?" we challenge LTD to consider themselves as part of that future. Leasing the land is a viable option that allows LTD to stay involved in the development of this area now and throughout the future.

Public-Private Partnerships

Source: Farming First (2010)

Housing funding options

An additional concern for our team's planning project for Old Station is the provision of affordable housing. Considering the current population forecast given for Eugene, Old Station can also expect to grow. Current predictions estimate that upwards of 4,000 of Eugene's anticipated 40,000 new residents may move to the River Road Santa Clara neighborhood over the next 20 years.²⁵ As new residents move to the area, the increased housing demand will need to be met. However, overall trends summarized earlier in this report (such as the high housing value-to-income ratio) indicate the challenge and decrease of housing affordability for Old Station. Future planning needs to account for the provision of affordable housing options for development proposals in the area.

A stated pillar in Envision Eugene is to:

"Provide housing affordable housing to all income levels."³⁹

Currently, Eugene is awarded Community Development Block Grants and Home Investment Partnership Program funds from the federal government to support current affordable housing initiatives.⁴⁰ Other strategies include neighborhood proposals for urban reserves, growth monitoring, collaborative planning efforts with various stakeholders (e.g., city, business, and residential interests), affordable housing development projects, and a Multi-Unit Property Tax Exemption option, among other approaches.⁴⁰

However, as the Eugene City Council notes, current access to affordable housing is still inadequate and poses significant challenges for residents.⁴⁰ In addition to increasing housing supply through redevelopment, an analysis of the Arlington County Transit-Oriented Development (TOD) approach offers some useful insights to address Old Station's housing affordability challenges. For Arlington, their TOD project led to a steep rise in property values which ultimately increased housing costs and significantly affected the availability of affordable housing options in the corridor.²⁷ The county initially sought to address this beginning in the 1990s by protecting existing

affordable housing and developing new options along the corridor. Their approach included the provision of "community benefit units" (CBUs) by nonprofits and individuals and has helped meet some demand for affordable housing near transit stations. CBUs are promoted by county policies which provide a thirty-year guarantee to nonprofits and individuals offering housing affordability options. 2001 estimates indicated the presence of 1,783 CBUs out of the 22,708 housing units along the corridor.²⁷

Additionally, the containment of the TOD project along the corridor (within a half mile radius from each of the stations) has helped retain existing affordable housing located outside of the corridor's well-defined development boundaries.³² Arlington County's successful push for residential developments has kept pace with housing demand in the area and also helped reduce high housing costs. The county has also taken a proactive approach for any new development. As part of the site plan review process, developers must provide one of two options—either affordable on-site units or affordable housing fund contributions to future off-site affordable housing construction projects. As of 2004, Arlington County contributions to affordable housing initiatives ranged from \$1 to \$2 million dollars annually. To further preserve affordable housing the county board enacted a stipulation in 1990 called the "Special Affordable Housing Protection District," which mandates one-for-one unit replacements.²⁷

While Arlington continues to address the challenge of providing affordable housing, there are some useful approaches for Old Station to consider. Containing development within a traditional TOD half-mile radius from the station may be one way to help preserve existing affordable housing located outside of that boundary. Another technique to consider is requiring developers to provide affordable housing on-site or, alternatively, to contribute to an "Affordable Housing Trust Fund" for future off-site affordable housing projects.

Implementation and Phases

Coordinated Implementation

Four Corners

- **Northeast Corner:** LTD old station, this is our catalyst site and the first stage of implementation with a large mixed-use building featuring a community center and ground floor businesses with residential units above. Location of placemaking elements; fountain and mural.
- **Southeast Corner:** Location of new Northbound LTD EMX stop on the corner of River Rd. and River Ave. Site of shopping center retrofits and medium density, mixed-use residential units with central pedestrian corridor.
- **Southwest Corner:** Location of Southbound LTD EMX stop and additional shopping center retrofits for local businesses with row houses and/or townhome residential units
- **Northwest Corner:** Mixed use building with strong emphasis on community and social services like a day care and senior center with residential units and additional placemaking elements.

Vision: The Four Corners on River Road

1. We propose a community catalyst site on the Northeast corner of the River Road, River Avenue intersection on the former site of the old LTD park-and-ride bus station. The primary structure on site will be a new 6 story mixed-use building. It will contain ground floor retail and the new River Road neighborhood Community Center. The building will have 80 new housing units. Using traditional 20% inclusionary zoning the building will contain 16 new affordable housing units, the rest going at market rate. This will bring much needed affordable housing and new economic opportunities to the neighborhood. The building will serve as the anchor of the site and a buffer to the Randy Pape Beltline Highway. Behind the building plantings of Emerald Arborvitae trees will act as a noise, emissions and wind barrier, mitigating the negative effects of highway traffic. In the plaza space outside the building there will be a small parking lot, and a fountain honoring the neighborhood's connection to the Willamette River and its Native American heritage. By the fountain will be a new playground complete with age appropriate sections for younger as well as older children. Around the playground and set inside the plaza will be numerous park benches, tables and chairs bordered by a wall mural depicting the history of the River Road neighborhood and the North Eugene High School mascot, the Highlanders. Along the eastern edge of the site in the area of the former bus slipway will be a bicycle share station and e-scooter sharing station in order to increase sustainable mobility and offer "last mile" public transit solutions.
2. The Southeast corner of the River Road, River Avenue intersection will feature the bulk of the Four Corners development, anchored by the new EmX bus stop nearest to the intersection and a retrofitted shopping center at its heart. To the south of the bus stop will be a new cafe and coffee shop complete with an outdoor dining section that overlooks the rest of the development. Surrounding it will be the pedestrian only heart of the Four Corners development. The pedestrian only center will be intersected by numerous new paths and sidewalks designed to bring pedestrians in from the activated street corners to the heart of the site. Though it will be a pedestrian only center, the pathways will

be wide enough to accommodate emergency and service vehicles when necessary, a design feature pioneered by the Vauban district in Freiburg, Germany.⁴¹ The pedestrian center will contain a community garden and small amphitheater designed for plays and other community programs. The area will feature native plants in elevated planters and rain gardens for landscaping. Five large structures will surround the heart of the development as mixed-use buildings featuring ground floor retail and social services with mixed income apartments on the upper floors. These will follow the inclusionary zoning model of 20 percent affordable housing established by the initial structure on the Northeast corner. Several of the buildings will feature small pocket parks with green walls where residents can rest and gather. The Southern end of the section will contain the main parking lot for the development with areas designated for residents and shoppers. A section of the parking lot will be marked to function as a weekend market and parking for food trucks during special events. A new street will run from Corliss Lane in the South to River Avenue in the North marking the Eastern edge of the site. Along its Eastern side will be a row of new two-story townhomes with on street parking. The townhomes will act as a soft edge helping the development blend in with the single-family homes around it more harmoniously than the taller units in the center of the site.

3. The Southwest corner of the development will feature street facing row houses with mixed-income housing units. Parking will be in the rear, between the row houses and several new mixed-use development buildings featuring ground floor retail and additional housing units on their upper floors. This corner will host the southbound EmX bus stop which will be directly across from the new Northbound stop on the other side of River Road. They will be connected by an elevated crosswalk that bisects a new planted median running from the intersection of River Road and the Beltway to the intersection of River Road and Corliss Lane. This planted median will act as a traffic calming measure and provide a halfway point for pedestrians crossing River Road.
4. The Northwest Corner, at the intersection of Silver Lane and River Road will somewhat mirror the Northeast corner of the development. It too will be anchored by a new mixed-use building with ground floor businesses and mixed-income apartments above. The building will host a new day care as well as the new River Road Senior Center. It will have a small playground for young children and park furniture for seniors designed specifically for games like chess. The building will also host a study lounge for North Eugene High School students. In combining these social services, the Northwest Corner of the Four Corners development will serve as a unifying element of the neighborhood, bringing together multiple generations in community and fellowship.

These plans are in keeping with the principles of the River Road and Santa Clara Neighborhood plan and principles, Envision Eugene, Eugene 2035 Transportation Plan, and LTD's Moving Ahead plan. They will require public-private cooperation, but can bring a newfound sense of community and opportunity to the River Road neighborhood through transit-oriented development that is human scaled, safe, walkable and sustainable.

Old Station Design Concepts

Accessibility and Connectivity:

- EmX Transit Station: MovingAhead¹ and Eugene 2035 Transportation Plan⁴² see the EmX Transit alternative as offering the greatest benefit to pedestrian and cyclist connectivity. LTD is planning on replacing the Old Station with the new EmX station at the corner of River Road and River Ave. We propose moving the station directly south of River Avenue so transit riders board and exit the bus further away from the highway, mitigating safety issues, and closer to retail and community amenities, providing a more welcoming experience for riders.
- Pedestrian access: Our design concepts surrounding pedestrian safety and accessibility are also in line with Eugene 2035. We support their plan to build a pedestrian/cyclist bridge across the Beltline Highway, near North Eugene High School, to connect residents to the north side of the highway and provide an alternate route to using the congested, dangerous River Road. Additional pedestrian safety and accessibility options include:
 - Raised crosswalks on the intersection of River Road and River Avenue
 - Well-lit crosswalks
 - Enhanced crosswalks and creative street design
 - Tree canopy lining the roads
- Cyclist access: Improving cyclist safety and connectivity to the surrounding amenities on River Road is essential to increasing cyclist traffic in this neighborhood. We propose developing protected bike lanes along River Road to improve safety and make cyclists feel welcome. Eugene 2035 already plans on implementing protected bicycle lanes from Division Avenue, just north of the Beltline Highway, south to the Northwest Expressway. Additional cyclist proposals include:
 - Connecting the bicycle lane at our intersection to the Willamette River path
 - Improving signage along the river path so people are aware of surrounding amenities on River Road
 - Expanding the bicycle lane for additional access to North Eugene High School from Kourt Drive south of the school and Silver Lane north of the school

Affordable Housing and Mixed-use Buildings:

- To accommodate for future population growth in the neighborhood and to account for the lower socioeconomic demographics of its residents, we propose developing affordable, multi-family housing along River Road.
- Through collaborating with private owners and developers who own the outdated strip malls, we propose retrofitting these areas and developing mixed-use buildings with improved pedestrian connectivity to the retail and food centers on the first floor of these buildings.
- To address affordable housing concerns, we proposed containing development within a traditional TOD half mile radius from the station may be one way to help preserve existing affordable housing located outside of that boundary.
- We also propose that the city consider requiring developers to provide affordable housing on-site or, alternatively, to contribute to an “Affordable Housing Trust Fund” for future off-site affordable housing projects.

Placemaking:

- We suggest a placemaking approach that starts with a shift in strategic questions from “what should we do?” to “who are we becoming as a community?” asking stakeholders to share their stories and using this input to inform placemaking projects. We envision proposals that provide diverse economic opportunities for local businesses, value community health outcomes that prioritize jobs and income as much as a sense of belonging and leadership and create opportunities for organizations that promote the brand of River Road.
- Physical manifestations of these placemaking efforts, designed with the River Road community and its heritage in mind, could result in

things like:

- Public art
- Water features
- Historical signage
- Wayfinding maps
- Physical spaces designed for community gatherings
- Programming and activities for the entire neighborhood

Sustainability:

- Strict energy usage guidelines for on-site buildings
- A complete streets approach with large urban tree canopy to promote walkability and shade buildings.
- Sustainable transportation options on site like bicycle share and e-scooter stations.
- Pursuing LEED certification for buildings larger than 30,000 sf on site.
- A new city ordinance requiring cool roofs or green roofs on structures larger than 20,000 sf.
- Public-private partnerships to offer incentives for onsite renewable energy such as solar photovoltaic panels.
- Extensive stormwater management through the use of rainwater catchment systems, rain gardens, bioswales and permeable paving solutions where appropriate.
- Landscaped pocket parks providing an urban oasis for residents.
- Native vegetation and a community garden where residents can grow their own food for consumption and sale.

Policy Adoptions

TOD framework

As a concept, TOD is defined as mixed-use, mixed-density development occurring inside a half-mile radius from a transit station.²⁷ This measurement reflects the normative area of acceptable walking distance most residents are willing to take during a commute. However, as Dittmar and Ohland observe, TOD projects must go beyond the physical form and functionally to integrate not only with transit but with the greater surrounding community.²⁷ The approach of complementing the purpose of a place with the community's needs illustrates the importance of placemaking in the successful implementation of TOD. If done well, TOD can lead to positive outcomes related to enhanced neighborhood livability. These outcomes include fostering neighborhood identity and vibrancy, the creation of a healthy pedestrian environment, interconnected streets, increased transit options, and availability of mixed housing types.³²

The Arlington case study illustrates the importance of early, organized, and ongoing community engagement to foster greater project success. Fortunately, the Old Station site located along the River Road corridor in Eugene, Oregon represents an area in which City of Eugene project leaders have had ongoing engagement with the River Road Santa Clara neighborhood community.⁹ For any future development project to succeed, a collaborative process involving a wide range of actors (i.e., city planners, neighborhood associations, developers, businesses, and property owners) in which the primary goal is to realize the community's vision will continue to be of paramount importance.²⁷ To finance redevelopment, city officials may want to consider adopting a similar policy to Arlington County, requiring developers to finance public infrastructure improvements as part of their development project.

Arlington's "bull's-eye" approach to concentrate high and mid-density development directly around the transit stations reflects a preference for a similar approach along the River Road corridor. The River Road Corridor Study showed that participants supported concentrated development along four neighborhood centers.⁹ For the Old Station site specifically, related research indicates that sites with large surface parking lots are prime areas for TOD projects.³² Notably, Goal 14 of the River Road Santa Clara Neighborhood Plan advocates for privacy transitions between low- and high-density areas.⁶ If a TOD approach creating high density neighborhoods was implemented for the Old Station site, additional steps need to be taken to buffer existing uses between areas.

Community Engagement

There are five themed vision statements in the River Road and Santa Clara Neighborhood plan. The draft vision statement for Community states,

"The River Road and Santa Clara Neighborhoods exude a strong sense of place. They are welcoming and inclusive neighborhoods for people of all backgrounds. River Road and Santa Clara celebrate and nurture community unity and diverse cultures, while honoring the rich history of farming in the neighborhoods. The community recognizes the value of natural assets, such as the River, and thriving shared spaces, such as parks, schools and local businesses. Our neighborhoods are safe, resilient, and engaged, with strong social networks and reliable public services."⁶

Accordingly, our vision also prioritizes community identity and unity and it is important to us that the River Road community feel some level of ownership in the development that happens on the Four Corners of River Road. One strategy that we suggest for public participation and community engagement is Sensemaking. A concept

based on Neil Takemoto's tools for co-creation and sensemaking that center a community's health in the process of community development. In the article titled *Co-creating places start with collecting stories, sensemaking* Takemoto comments, "a community's health is often measured by explicit outcomes (e.g. income, jobs, crime) over intrinsic outcomes (e.g. belonging, compassion, leadership), resulting in a dominance of investment in those explicit outcomes. This one-sided investment severely inhibits meaningful growth in intrinsic outcomes, inhibiting extrinsic outcomes as well."⁴³ In order to fulfill the vision set forth in the River Road Neighborhood plan, any development must consider how place is also about community health, and it is one of many tools that can be used to establish a relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic outcomes in planning. While thinking about our site, we would be wise to shift our strategic questions from the notion of "what should we do?" to "who are we becoming as a people?"⁴³ and how to make the spaces we occupy reflect this.

Takemoto suggests that the most powerful problem-solving systems are when people engage in authentic participation. The vision we have for the Four Corners on River Road will involve a great deal of community engagement and participation if this place strives to reflect the character of the community. As outsiders coming in, one approach planners ought to consider starts with sincerely listening to the stakeholders in the community. Takemoto lays this approach out in a five-step process:

1. **Stories** are collected from the people in the community
2. The people **make sense** of what the collective stories are trying to say.
3. The people **self-organize** based on aligned interests.
4. The people **co-create** solutions.
5. The people **co-invest** in those solutions, and repeat the cycle.⁴³

This is what Takemoto refers to as a system of emergence, or the point at which there are tangible outputs and outcomes from a group of people (a community) collaborating. In practice, each of these steps would be followed by the planners engaging community in public participation. The Stories are collected from community members through a sensemaking program in which folks give meaning to their collective experience. The idea behind sensemaking is to shift the focus of organization studies from how decisions shape organizations to how meaning drives organizing. In effect, experience and collective experience are considered meaningful and used to create a shared understanding from different perspectives and interests. Next, the sensemaking results are displayed in maps or by trends for the community to better understand one another. Then, based on aligned interests people self-organize into groups or networks and often this leads to the organic emergence of leadership and solutions. Now that community members have self-organized into informed and energized groups, co-created solutions come to fruition. Lastly, is the co-investment phase. Members establish a system of co-ownership of their creative content, ideas, and solutions and have a sense of ownership for the outcomes of their labor.

Community Planning Process

Source: River Road Corridor Study (2019)

An approach such as sensemaking is but one way to engage the community. That said, this approach centers the community as the experts of their own experience and the most equipped to inform planners, developers and decision-makers. Our vision aims to create a neighborhood brand for the River Road area that captures the character of their community. It would be naive and nearly impossible to accomplish this without involving and deriving meaning from the stories of community stakeholders. Efforts towards placemaking that capture the community's visions, honor the heritage and history of the area, and create opportunity for River Road residents can only succeed if those community members are directly involved in informing the development process.

Ultimately, regardless of how much data we gather, how many case studies we examine or alternatives we suggest, the River Road community members will need to be involved in co-creating solutions and informing decisions about what makes sense for the development in their own neighborhoods.

Community Planning Process

Source: River Road Corridor Study (2019)

Phasing

Our vision for Old Station requires coordinated implementation for projects with a phased approach over a 30-year timeframe. *The phases below are in 5-year increments: Phase 0, 0-5 years; Phase I, 6-10 years; Phase II, 11-15 years; Phase III, 16-20 years.

Implementation Strategy	Phase*	Responsible Party
Concept 1: Connectivity and Accessibility		
Review existing zoning <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - City parking requirements - Propose removal of minimum parking requirements - Analyze if density zoning fits within density gradient of concept plan - Propose zone changes if necessary 	0	City
Sell or Lease the LTD Old Station	0	Lane Transit District (LTD)
Move the EmX station just south of the River Road intersection	0	LTD
Make bike lanes and sidewalks safer and clearer at our intersection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implement protected/buffered bike lanes along River Road - Use context-sensitive design and widen sidewalks for pedestrians - Install wayfinding signs for cyclists and pedestrians 	0	LTD
Create safer crossings at River Rd/Silver Ln intersection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Install flashing lighted crosswalks - Use pavement markings and creative street design to increase crosswalk visibility 	0	LTD
New EmX	I	LTD
Extend the bike path from the river pathway	I	City
Create bicycle bridges in the Silver Lane neighborhood	I	City
Create new pedestrian walkways on smaller roads <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identify areas currently in need of new sidewalk construction - Construct sidewalks along main school routes 	I	City

- Implement neighborhood walking routes along alleyways		
Road diet for River Rd. between Beltline & Corliss Ln. complete with planted median and room for proposed EMX lane	I	LTD/City
Require new construction to reduce surface parking lots to a minimum	I, II	City/Private
Concept 2: Mixed-use buildings and spaces		
Review existing zoning and policies <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - policy implementation providing affordable housing price guarantees - new site plan review requirements to build or fund affordable housing projects 	0, I	City
Identify ideal sites of context-responsive infill for Old Station site area	0	City
Incentivize private redevelopment of strip malls on the four corners. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invite developers to a community meeting to talk about economic opportunities for local business - Brainstorm business ideas that fit into the RR brand - Open RFP 	0, I, II, III	City
Redevelop the northeast corner of the Old Station site with a mixed-use building and public space	0, I	City/Partnership
Create infill in the empty parking lot space in the strip malls	I	Private
Buffer existing uses between low- and high-density areas	I, II, III	City/Partnership
Continue mixed-use building development and affordable, multi-family housing (i.e., construct high-density buildings on each of the corners to provide amenities, housing, and services)	II, III	City/Partnership
Retrofitting strip malls. Redeveloping this buildable land to provide mixed-use buildings with residential and commercial elements to cater to the future population's needs.	III	Private/City
Concept 3: Placemaking: Enhancing the Neighborhood Character and Vibrancy		
Engaging the community through focused public participation workshops		

	0, I, II, III	City
Construct community center on the northeast corner of the Old Station	I	City/Partnership
Place-making <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community engagement: sensemaking - Stakeholder stories inform placemaking projects - Prioritize community organizations that fit the RR brand - Bilingual signage around the area - River bike path historical informational/wayfinding signs - Create programming in community gathering spaces 	I, II, III	City/Neighborhood groups/Community stakeholders
Identifying places on the master plan	0	City developers, Architects and Planners
Creating economic and mixed-use nodes		Planners and City developers
Installation of public art, murals, sculptures, wayfinding etc.	I, II, III	Artists, Architects and Planners

Conclusion

This plan for Old Station was created with the following question in mind: Where do we want to go together?

The Old Station site offers vast opportunity to introduce vibrancy into the neighborhood and provide a safe sense of place for residents. Through the implementation of mixed-use buildings, placemaking elements, pedestrian/cyclist connectivity, and accessibility elements we are able to cater to the needs of the current and future residents in the surrounding neighborhood. Ensuring community engagement is utilized during implementation is key to a successful redevelopment of the area that properly represents the current and future needs of the River Road residents. Together we can create a future for the River Road neighborhood that is vibrant, safe, walkable, sustainable and accessible for all.

Source: OregonLive(2015)

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Appendix

FIGURE 6. AGE DISTRIBUTION – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2017

Source: ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Social Explorer Table A01001

TABLE 3. SELECTED INDUSTRY – LANE COUNTY, 2001-2016

Industry	2001		2016		Change	
	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	Employment (#)	Employment (%)	#	%
Manufacturing	21,032	11.4%	15,260	7.5%	-5,772	-27.4%
Retail Trade	22,160	12.0%	24,428	11.9%	2,268	10.2%
Educational Services	2,334	1.3%	4,222	2.1%	1,888	80.9%
Health Care and Social Assistance	2,353	11.0%	28,469	13.9%	8,116	39.9%

Source: NAICS

TABLE 5. LOCATION QUOTIENT – LANE COUNTY, 2001-2016

Sector	2001	2016
Manufacturing	1.11	1.10
Retail Trade	1.09	1.19
Educational Services	0.69	0.85
Health Care and Social Assistance	1.19	1.23

Source: NAICS

TABLE 6. POPULATION-EMPLOYMENT RATIOS – UNITED STATES, OREGON, AND LANE COUNTY, 2001-2016

Sector	UNITED STATES		OREGON		LANE COUNTY	
	2001	2016	2001	2016	2001	2016
Manufacturing	16.8	24.6	15.3	19.9	15.5	24.0
Retail Trade	15.6	16.6	14.8	16.0	14.7	15.0
Educational Services	94.6	68.4	100.3	66.9	139.6	86.7
Health Care and Social Assistance	18.7	14.7	18.0	14.1	16.0	12.9

Source: NAICS

FIGURE 7. FAMILY POVERTY RATES – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Source: ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Social Explorer Table A13002

FIGURE 9. POVERTY RATE – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2017

Source: ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Table DP03

TABLE 9. PERCENT CHANGE IN RENT-TO-INCOME RATIO - OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Median Rent and Income	Oregon	Lane County	Eugene	CT 28
Gross Rent (dollars)	35.7%	22.6%	20.0%	33.5%
Household Income (dollars)	13.9%	11.2%	13.9%	6.2%

Sources:

ACS 2006-2010 (5-Year Estimates), Tables S1901 and B25063

ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Tables S1901 and B25063

FIGURE 10. HOUSING TENURE - OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2010-2017

Sources:
 Census 2010, Table SE:T69
 ACS 2017 (5-Year Estimates), Table A10060

FIGURE 11. COST BURDEN ASSESSMENT FOR GROSS RENT – OREGON, LANE COUNTY, EUGENE, AND CENSUS TRACT 28, 2017

Sources:
 ACS 2006-2010 (5-Year Estimates), Tables A18009 and B25063
 ACS 2013-2017 (5-Year Estimates), Tables A18009 and B25063

